

Viscosity B Coefficient of Phenols and Benzyl Alcohol

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THE viscosity B coefficient of Jones-Dole's equation is known to be sensitive to the nature of solute-solvent interactions, i.e. it is related to the modification of micro-viscosity of the solvent in the neighbourhood of the solute particle as compared to the bulk viscosity. A structure-making solute is expected to have a positive B coefficient in the given solvent whereas a structure-breaker may have a less positive or altogether negative B coefficient¹. However, a large solute may always possess a positive B coefficient (irrespective of the nature of its interaction with the solvent) due to the "obstruction effect", i.e., a bending of the solvent streamlines round a large solute particle. The sign and magnitude of the temperature coefficient, $\frac{dB}{dT}$, rather than B, therefore, often provides a better index of solute-solvent interactions. This observation is attributed to an increased thermal mobility of water molecules at higher temperatures which causes the structure-promotion by a solute more difficult (i.e., B is rendered less positive) so that $\frac{dB}{dT}$ becomes negative. A structure-breaker, on the other hand, exerts a less disruptive influence on the structure of the solvent (which is already broken) at an elevated temperature, and hence the corresponding $\frac{dB}{dT}$ is positive. These considerations are obviously independent of the size of the solute particle.

In the present study, viscosity B coefficient of phenol, resorcinol, *p*-cresol and benzyl alcohol has been determined in aqueous medium at temperatures 30, 35 and 40°. The magnitude and sign of $\frac{dB}{dT}$ at 35° is also ascertained for each solute. The B coefficients were obtained by having recourse to a graphical technique based on Jones-Dole's equation,

$$\text{namely, } \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad \dots (1)$$

where η_0 and η are the respective viscosity coefficients, at the same temperature, of pure water and the solution of molar concentration C , while A and B are empirical constants, sensitive to solute-solute interactions (Grüneisen effect) and solute-solvent interactions.

A rearrangement of eq. (1) leads to

$$\frac{\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1}{\sqrt{C}} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad \dots (2)$$

so that a plot of $\frac{\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1}{\sqrt{C}}$ vs \sqrt{C} gives a straight

line of slope B and intercept A.

An Ubbelohde type of viscometer with an average flow time of 502 sec for 10 ml of water (at 30°) was used for viscosity determinations. AnalaR grade materials, whenever available, have been used; otherwise, the purest grade available has been further purified. The solutions were prepared in deionised water of conductivity less than $3 \mu \text{ mho cm}^{-1}$. The temperatures of study have been kept constant within $\pm 0.05^\circ$ by the use of a water thermostat provided with an electrical contact thermometer along with a solid-state relay unit.

The results have been entered in Table 1. That the B coefficient of phenol at lower temperatures (e.g. 30°) is higher than that of resorcinol, but lower than the value for *p*-cresol, is consistent with a corresponding change in the net content of hydrophobic (e.g. methyl) and hydrophilic (e.g. hydroxyl) groups in these compounds. An increase in the former (as in *p*-cresol) is expected to lead to an increase in the B coefficient in aqueous medium, due to structure-promotion in water through what is known as "hydrophobic hydration"². Resorcinol, with a higher content of structure-breaking hydroxyl groups, has the lowest B (at 30°). Aliphatic compounds, belonging to a particular homologous series (e.g. the carboxylates), also exhibit a similar increase in B coefficient with the lengthening of the hydrophobic carbon chain³. However, the B values for phenols are found, on comparison with those for aliphatic carboxylates, surprisingly small for six-carbon solutes (intermediate between the values for two- and three-carbon carboxylates³); this low contribution of a phenyl group may have arisen from the inability of water molecules to accommodate themselves inside the benzene ring for spatial restrictions. Such a partial loss of structure-making (i.e. "ordering") influence of methylene groups, induced by "aromaticity", is in line with the general higher water-solubilities of aromatic compounds as compared to the open-chain analogues, having the same number of carbon atoms (i.e., due to a lower "negentropy" effect of the aromatic compounds on water structure).

A positive $\frac{dB}{dT}$ at 35° for resorcinol, whereas the negative values for phenol and *p*-cresol (the latter having it more negative), are also in agreement with the generalisations made in the introductory part. Consequent of these opposite signs of $\frac{dB}{dT}$, B of phenol, at a high enough temperature such as 40°, is rendered lower than that of resorcinol.

The B coefficient of benzyl alcohol, a molecular isomer of *p*-cresol, exhibits a somewhat erratic

TABLE-1

		Viscosity of water (η_0) at			Density of water (ρ_0) at			
		30°=0.7975 cp 35°=0.7194 cp 40°=0.6529 cp			30°=0.9956 g cm ⁻³ 35°=0.9940 g cm ⁻³ 40°=0.9922 g cm ⁻³			
Solution	Molar concentration/M (C)	Coefficient of viscosity of solution/cp, η at			B coefficient (slope of linear plot of $\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0 \sqrt{C}}$ vs \sqrt{C}) at			$\frac{dB}{dT}$ at
		30°	35°	40°	30°	35°	40°	35°
Phenol	0.025	—	0.7235	0.6565	0.230	0.213	0.192	-0.0037
	0.05	0.8104	0.7280	0.6592				
	0.08	0.8177	0.7311	0.6627				
	0.10	0.8228	0.7348	0.6664				
	0.15	—	0.7432	0.6758				
	0.20	0.8434	—	—				
Resorcinol	0.03	0.7994	—	—	0.189	0.216	0.244	+0.0054
	0.05	0.8060	0.7288	0.6620				
	0.10	0.8140	0.7374	0.6706				
	0.15	—	0.7458	0.6786				
	0.20	—	0.7538	0.6867				
	0.25	—	0.7625	0.6954				
p-cresol	0.05	0.7956	0.7315	0.6632	0.366	0.326	0.295	-0.0065
	0.075	0.8031	0.7380	0.6683				
	0.10	0.8101	0.7432	0.6740				
	0.12	0.8163	0.7484	0.6797				
Benzyl alcohol	0.025	—	0.7244	0.6576	0.222	0.272	0.260	—
	0.05	—	0.7296	0.6626				
	0.075	0.8140	0.7345	0.6670				
	0.10	0.8200	0.7397	0.6712				
	0.15	0.8309	0.7512	0.6816				
	0.20	0.8406	—	—				
0.30	0.8629	—	—					

temperature-dependence (an increase in B with temperature followed by a small drop beyond 35°; the $\frac{dB}{dT}$ at 35° for benzyl alcohol is, therefore, not quoted in Table 1), even though the values are close to those for p-cresol. This perhaps results from a partial overlapping of the structure-making and structure-breaking spheres of influence of the hydrophobic methylene and hydrophilic hydroxy groups, situated in close proximity in the side-chain, -CH₂OH, in benzyl alcohol. This gets a qualitative support from similar observations reported for the enthalpy of transfer of methanol from water to heavy water (as compared to that for higher alcohols)⁴, as well as the reported heats of transport of α -alanine and β -alanine in aqueous medium⁵.

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The Reaction of Isatin with Active Methylene Group. Part—I: Formation of 5-(2-Oxo-3-Indolinyldiene)-3-Aryl-2,4-Thiazolidindiones—
A New Class of Thioindigoid Dyes

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THE methylene group of substances having the structure -COCH₂NH- condenses readily with the carbonyl group of aldehydes and ketones¹. Active methylene group present in the 4-thiazolidinone ring has also been found to react with aryldiazonium salts² and isatino carbonyl group³.

A number of derivatives of isatin- β -thiosemicarbazone are reported to have antiviral activity⁴. Because of their usefulness and in order to examine the reactivity of the methylene group of 2,4-thiazolidindiones, we have undertaken the preparation of 5-(2-oxo-3-indolinyldiene)-3-aryl-2,4-thiazolidindiones which form a new class of thioindigoid dyes.

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